

A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews

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Abstract

Context: A number of conduct standards and reporting checklists have been published to support researchers in planning, doing, and writing up scientifically rigorous systematic reviews (SRs). However, compliance with SR conduct standards and reporting checklists remains a significant challenge.

Objective: We hypothesise that compliance with conduct standards and checklists can be improved by reducing the amount of experience required for successfully using such standards and checklists in a research process.

Methods: To set the initial groundwork for testing this hypothesis, we developed a proof-of-concept general-purpose SR protocol using the protocols.io platform, modified the output to consist of labelled data, and developed code and a template for automated creation of a draft protocol manuscript from the labelled data.

Discussion: Creating the operational process for SR protocol planning and the technology stack for automated documentation allowed us to develop our theoretical understanding of how such a system may improve compliance with research conduct and reporting standards. This includes the potential value of algorithmic rather than heuristic approaches to conducting and reporting research studies, positioning of labelled data rather than a study manuscript as the primary product of the research process, and viewing the process of developing research standards as being analogous to development of open software. Finally, we identified specific and general issues in our technology stack that would need to be addressed to enable further development and testing of our proposed approach.

29 Introduction

30 A number of conduct standards and reporting checklists have been published to support
31 researchers in planning, doing, and writing up scientifically rigorous systematic reviews (SRs).
32 However, compliance with SR conduct standards and reporting checklists appears to be a
33 significant challenge for researchers, with consistent evidence of shortcomings in the
34 methodological rigour and comprehensiveness of documentation of SRs from a range of
35 research fields including healthcare (Page *et al.*, 2016; Gao *et al.*, 2019), environmental science
36 (Pullin *et al.*, 2022), socioeconomics (Wang *et al.*, 2021), and human environmental health
37 (Menon, Struijs and Whaley, 2022). This is potentially a significant source of research waste or
38 even societal harm, with significant resources being used to conduct SRs that may be
39 redundant, present inaccurate findings, or both (Ioannidis, 2016).

40 Conduct standards specify sets of requirements that a SR needs to meet in order to attain a
41 certain level of scientific quality. The intent is to provide researchers with a list of criteria that, if
42 met, should ensure a SR has some desired combination of usefulness, credibility (e.g. by
43 reducing bias), and transparency (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). We believe one important
44 obstacle to compliance with conduct standards is their complexity, which creates a high
45 experience requirement on the part of researchers for their successful use. SR standards tend
46 to be lengthy, with the Institute of Medicine guidance on SRs consisting of 82 performance
47 elements and extensive narrative text (Institute of Medicine, 2011), the Cochrane MECIR
48 standard of over 75 elements accompanied by a handbook of over 700 pages (Cochrane, 2019;
49 Higgins, JPT *et al.*, 2019), and the COSTER recommendations for SRs of environmental health
50 research of 70 elements (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). Such length and complexity is probably
51 unavoidable when formalising the necessary components of a research process that is in itself
52 lengthy and complex; however, it presents a considerable organisational challenge to
53 successfully comply with each and every component of a standard. There is an important
54 difference between knowing what to do (the requirement presented in the standard) and
55 knowing how to do it successfully (the resourcing, planning, training, etc. necessary to meet the
56 requirement that is not specified in the standard).

57 Reporting checklists are intended to support authors in providing enough information about
58 what they did and found in the course of conducting a SR that a reader can follow their methods
59 and appraise the credibility of their results (Moher *et al.*, 2014). As for conduct standards, we
60 believe there is a high experience requirement for their successful use. One aspect of this
61 experience requirement is the necessity for users and writers of a checklist to share the same

62 understanding of how terms describing checklist items map onto the processes of a systematic
63 review. Ways in which this can break down in a PRISMA report (Page *et al.*, 2021), for example,
64 include the misidentification of risk of bias with other study appraisal methods, and the
65 conflation of the Population-Exposure-Comparator-Outcome (PECO) statement for describing
66 the objectives of a SR with PECO-derived eligibility criteria of a SR (Menon, Struijs and Whaley,
67 2022). Further complicating things, reporting checklists imply a certain set of recommended
68 practices that may not be explicit and might not have been followed by the research team using
69 the checklist. Proficiency in the technical jargon and implied practices in systematic review
70 requires a potentially lengthy period of acculturation in relevant, competent communities of
71 practice. Seen in those terms, successful use of checklists could be as much an indicator of
72 successful acculturation as they are a facilitator of writing up rigorous SR manuscripts.

73 We hypothesise that the experience requirement for successful use of standards and
74 checklists may be lowered by (1) interpreting the recommendations of a conduct standard into a
75 sequence of operational steps that can be followed by a research team, and (2) recording what
76 is done in each operational step in such a way that data can later be automatically retrieved for
77 a given reporting task. To provide a foundation for testing this hypothesis and exploring the
78 technical requirements of such a system, we set out to build a general-purpose operational
79 template for planning and reporting a human environmental health SR. The template is
80 designed to have the following features:

- 81 1. Be an explicit, step-by-step sequence of operational procedures for developing and
82 documenting a human environmental health SR protocol;
- 83 2. A mapping of how each step in the template's operational procedure translates into
84 compliance with a selected set of conduct standards and reporting checklists;
- 85 3. Labelling of the steps and data outputs of the general protocol, to render machine-
86 readable the operational procedures and output data;
- 87 4. A script that automatically assembles from the labelled data a standards- and checklist-
88 compliant draft protocol document.

89 We emphasise that this is a proof-of-concept project. As far as we are aware, a general-
90 purpose operational protocol has not been developed for SRs, nor has automated
91 documentation from data gathered during SR protocol development been demonstrated. As a
92 proof of concept, our technology stack is a prototype and code has not been finessed. While we

93 have endeavoured to create something that could be useful in current form, the general-purpose
94 protocol primarily exists for testing and further development of ideas. We cover various aspects
95 of the limitations and development needs of our approach in the Discussion section, below.

96 **Materials and Methods**

97 *Development of the general purpose protocol*

98 For the general purpose protocol we revived an experimental build of a general-purpose SR
99 protocol based on the COSTER recommendations, created using the protocols.io bench
100 protocol platform (Whaley, 2020). COSTER is an adaptation for human environmental health
101 SRs of Cochrane's MECIR standard (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). To build the general-
102 purpose protocol, PW abstracted from COSTER all recommendations relevant to the planning
103 of a SR and interpreted them into a sequence of explicit operational steps. The resulting 41
104 operational steps include instructions on data that should be collected during each step and the
105 conditions under which each step should be marked as complete (Figure 1). PW then cross-
106 referenced each operational step against data reporting requirements for PRISMA-P (Moher *et*
107 *al.*, 2015), PRISMA-S (Rethlefsen *et al.*, 2021), ROSES for SR protocols (Haddaway *et al.*,
108 2018), and PROSPERO registrations (Booth *et al.*, 2012). Finally, PW created labels for each
109 operational step. The results of the cross-referencing and step labelling process are shown in
110 Table 1.

111 A run of the general purpose protocol requires users to input two types of data. For brief,
112 structured data, the user inputs data into the "smart component" feature of protocols.io (shown
113 in Figure 1). For complex, unstructured data, such as contextual justification for the SR, the user
114 creates a separate document, gives the document a specific name as per protocol instructions,
115 and adds it to an OSF archive. (This is a workaround for limits on data entry in the current
116 version of protocols.io.) Instructions for creating an archive, naming the documents, and a link to
117 an OSF template archive with pre-named template documents are included in the general
118 protocol. We created a script to parse the results of a protocol run and the content of the OSF
119 archive, and stitch the data together for automating the creation of draft protocol documentation.

Figure 1. Operationalisation into the general protocol of COSTER Recommendation 1.1.2: "Identify information management practices for each stage of the review, including reference and knowledge management tools, systematic review software, and statistics packages."

120 **Automation of protocol documentation**

121 We created a tool that extracts structured data from both protocols.io and the associated
 122 OSF records, cross-references these against existing SR reporting standards, and integrates
 123 the resulting data into reports according to a given template. In this project we only had capacity
 124 to develop one template, that is a complete report of the protocol planning process. However,
 125 third parties will be able to use our code and labelling to develop additional templates. The
 126 automated documentation process has two stages, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The process for automating the documentation of a protocol run. Arrows in blue represent interfaces secured using the OAuth2 authentication standard (<https://oauth.net/2/>).

127

128 The first stage of the process is retrieval. Here, the completed protocol (termed a “run” in
129 protocols.io) is retrieved from protocols.io using their API (<https://www.protocols.io/developers>).
130 Arrows in blue represent interfaces secured using the OAuth2 authentication standard
131 (<https://oauth.net/2/>). The current build of Protocols.io (accessed 7 July 2022) returns a JSON
132 document that consists of both data entered by the researcher, and other data including
133 formatting instructions for online display. We therefore had to write code to extract individual
134 fields from the protocol run via reference to structural features of the text (e.g. specific
135 punctuation and text block positions). The fields are assigned keys in a key-value store based
136 on the referenced standards to which they apply and the labels assigned to the step using
137 square brackets. For example, the entry "Endnote 20" above would be stored under the key
138 “info_manage” (label). For the entries that contain references to documents stored on the OSF
139 archive created during the protocol run, we retrieve the OSF record using their API
140 (<https://developer.osf.io/>). This yields a set of documents in Microsoft Word .docx format that
141 correspond to stages mentioned in the protocol run. We export the index to JSON and store the
142 documents separately on disk for later use. A sample of our JSON export is shown in Figure 3.

```
{
  "osf_record": "https://osf.io/zjevvp",
  "comp_infosci": "PW",
  "comp_eviapp": "PW, AB",
  "comp_stats": "SW, EF",
  "comp_topic": "AB, CD",
  "comp_srmeth": "PW",
  "comp_guarant": "PW",
  "info_refman": "Zotero",
  "info_knowman": "DistillerSR",
  "info_srsoft": "DistillerSR",
  "info_statspack": "R",
  "info_aitools": "Active Screener",
  "fund_sources": "SR Funder 100",
  "fund_funders": "Funded by general grant",
  "fund_grantnum": "12345",
  "fund_fundrole": "None",
  "interests": "https://osf.io/ejcyw",
  "need": "https://osf.io/vp7ak",
  "q_pop_species": "Human",
  "q_pop_sex": "Male",
  "q_pop_age": "45-65",
  "q_pop_health": "Healthy",
  "q_pop_add": "None",
  "q_exp_exp": "Phthalates",
  "q_exp_timing": "Before birth",
```

```

"q_exp_dur": "Any",
"q_exp_dose": "Any",
"q_exp_add": "None",
"q_comp_exp": "Lower levels of phthalate exposure",
"q_comp_timing": "Before birth",
"q_comp_dur": "Any",
"q_comp_dose": "Lower",
"q_comp_add": "Exclude studies with simulataneous exposure to
pesticides",
"q_out_primary": "Gout",
"q_out_second": "Kidney disease",
[truncated]
}
    
```

143 **Figure 3:** A truncated sample of structured data in JSON format, as extracted from the protocol run.

144 The second stage of the automated documentation system takes these data as input and
 145 reassembles them according to a template (an example template can be found at
 146 <https://osf.io/nckwu>). This supports two templating languages. The first is a simple subset of
 147 “mustache” markup, a widely-used templating language (<https://mustache.github.io/>). Here,
 148 entries from the JSON document representing structured data from the protocols.io run can be
 149 inserted into free text. For example, the entry “{{info_refman}}” is resolved to “Endnote 20”, as
 150 per the example in Figure 3. The second, an unnamed proprietary template language, allows
 151 template authors to include the contents of an external .docx file completely within the target
 152 document, allowing them to concatenate OSF records in any order. The output of this
 153 templating process is a Microsoft Word document. In our case, this is a complete summary of all
 154 data from the run, intended to be edited by the reviewer into a SR protocol manuscript;
 155 however, templates for PRISMA reports and other structured documents could also be created.

156 **Table 1.** Cross-walk of the top-level data labels and steps of the general-purpose protocol with items in the conduct
 157 standards and reporting checklists with which the protocol is designed to facilitate compliance. For a complete list of
 158 label definitions, see <https://osf.io/vw4e3>

Labels	Meaning of Labels	Step of General Protocol	Related Conduct Standard or Reporting Checklist Items				
			COSTER	PRISMA-P	PRISMA-S	ROSES	PROSPERO (human SRs)
osf_recor d	Title and URL of accompanying Open Science	1	-	1a, 1b	-	1	1

	Framework record						
competencies	Key competencies of the SR team	2	1.1.1	3b (partial)	16	-	6, 11
info_manage	Information management practices for the SR	3	1.1.2	11a	-	-	26
funding	Information about funding of the SR	4	-	5a, 5b, 5c	-	-	12
interests	Conflicts of interest management policy	5	1.1.3, 1.1.4	-	-	38	13
need	Explanation of need for the SR	6	1.2.1	6	-	5	-
rationale	The theoretical framework that supports the choice of question and use of SR methods to answer it.	7	1.2.2	6	-	5	-
question	The question being answered by the SR, characterised as a PECO statement	8	1.2.3	7, 12, 13	-	7, 8	15, 24, 25
eligibility	The eligibility criteria for evidence to be included in the SR	9	1.3	8	-	20	18-23
screening	The approach to screening evidence for eligibility for the SR	10	3.1	11b	-	18-20	26
multi_publics	The strategy for handling multiple	11	3.4	-	-	-	-

	publications from the same eligible study						
search	The search strategy for the SR	12	1.4.1, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6	9, 10	1-6, 8, 10, 11	9, 10, 15	16, 17
rerun_search	The plans for re-running the search	13	2.7	-	12	17	16
rob	The risk of bias assessment methods for the SR	14	1.4.3, 5.3, section 5	14	-	22, 23	27
other_appr	Other evidence appraisal methods to be used	15	7.8	-	-	22	-
char_incl	The planned characteristics of included studies table	16	1.4.2	-	-	-	-
extract_forms	The forms to be used for data extraction	17	1.4.7	12	-	-	-
synth	The methods to be used for synthesising the included evidence	18	1.4.4	15-16	-	30-34	28, 29
certainty	The methods to be used for assessing certainty in the results of the synthesis	19	1.4.5	17	-	23, 35,	-
integration	The methods to be used for integrating multiple streams of evidence	20	1.4.6	-	-	-	-

pilot_scre ening	Instruction to pilot the screening methods	21	1.4.7				
pilot_extr action	Instruction to pilot the data extraction forms	22	1.4.7	11c	-	25, 26	-
pilot_rob	Instruction to pilot the risk of bias assessment methods	23	1.4.7	-	-	-	-
pilot_cert ainty	Instruction to pilot the certainty assessment methods	24	1.4.7	-	-	-	-
write	Instruction to create a draft protocol document from the above steps	25	-	-	-	-	-
registratio n	Instructions and location data for registration of the protocol document	26	1.5.1	2	-	-	-
peer_revi ew	Instructions for peer-review of the protocol document	27	1.5.2	-	14	-	-
publicatio n	Instructions and location data for publication of the peer-reviewed protocol document	28	1.5.3	-	-	-	34
Items not covered in general template		PRISMA-P		Not covered: 2, 3a, 3b, 4. 12 is covered by rationale (protocol step 7)			
		PRISMA-S		Not covered: 7, 16. 9 is covered by eligibility criteria. 13, 15 not relevant for a protocol			
		ROSES		Not covered: 2, 3, 4, 6, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 21, 27, 29, 36, 37. 16 (search validation) should be added in a future update. 19, 22, 28: COSTER recommends duplicate screening and			

		appraisal so consistency checking is implicitly covered
	PROSPERO	Not covered: 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 14, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40. Mainly administrative data for PROSPERO

159

160 Expected Results

161 The general-purpose protocol is available at

162 <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldydzxl5b/v3>. A run of the general-purpose protocol
 163 yields three primary outputs:

- 164 1. A comprehensive record of key data that is needed for auditing standards compliance
 165 and/or writing up the planning process of a systematic review, generated in the process
 166 of recording the completion of each step of the operationalised general protocol.
- 167 2. Labelled SR protocol data that can be reassembled into any protocol documentation
 168 format, e.g. a conference abstract, PROSPERO registration, a protocol manuscript, a
 169 PRISMA report, a response to a data sharing request, etc.
- 170 3. After running the TARP code, a draft SR protocol manuscript. As a draft that merges
 171 labelled data into a fixed template, significant editing will be required, but the necessary
 172 information is approximately correctly located under relevant subheadings.

173 An example run consisting of a PDF showing what data was input during a test run of the
 174 general-purpose protocol, the processed JSON output from the test run, and an automatically
 175 generated .docx template created from the test run, are available at <https://osf.io/m35px/>
 176 (“Protocol publication” section). Code for the JSON conversion and .docx document generation
 177 is available at <https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD>.

178 Discussion

179 *Comparison to similar tools*

180 We did not do a systematic review of existing tools for this project, but we did search for
 181 similar initiatives from a number of sources. PW screened all GitHub records tagged as

182 “systematic-review”, “systematic-reviews”, or “systematic-literature-reviews”, the first 10 pages
183 of results of a Google search for “automated reporting of systematic reviews”, the first 100
184 results sorted by relevance for searching “systematic review” on the protocols.io platform, the
185 protocol and reporting tools indexed in the Systematic Review Toolbox
186 (<http://systematicreviewtools.com/>), and the SR support tools reviewed by Kohl et al. (2018).
187 PW also followed up on word-of-mouth recommendations received from discussion of this
188 project with our peers. For any tool that looked potentially similar to the present project, PW
189 checked public documentation of tool features for information about its functionality. Given the
190 limited documentation that often accompanies tools, we note that our descriptions of a tool may
191 not be a true reflection of the tool’s actual feature set.

192 The majority of GitHub records seemed to consist of document classifiers designed to
193 support the screening of search results for a SR, along with some tools to support the
194 development of search strategies. We did not find anything obviously related to facilitating
195 standard or checklist compliance. While protocols.io has been used as a repository for SR
196 protocols, no SRs appear to have been constructed as operational procedures in the platform.
197 Methods-Wizard from the SR-Accelerator (Clark *et al.*, 2020) does have features that generate
198 methods text from input data, but it does not seem to generate labelled data that is designed to
199 be machine-readable, and it does not obviously operationalise the step-by-step process of
200 developing a SR protocol. We did note the existence of a tool for reporting trials in behavioural
201 sciences, the Paper Authoring Tool (West, 2020), that generates labelled data, has features for
202 automated drafting of a manuscript, and covers some aspects of standards compliance
203 (although without explicit crosswalking). It was not clear if the Paper Authoring Tool is intended
204 to be completed retrospectively, or is a tool that also operationalises the process of planning a
205 study in a way that facilitates compliance with conduct standards.

206 Cochrane’s RevMan software for conducting SRs of health research (Cochrane, 2020)
207 appears to be the closest relative of our general-purpose protocol (desktop version 5.4.1,
208 released 21 September 2020). RevMan connects components of a SR protocol or final report to
209 the individual requirements of the MECIR standards, which in turn direct authors to detailed
210 methodological guidance in the relevant sections of the Cochrane Handbook. However,
211 RevMan is a reporting-focused tool that leaves implicit the step-by-step procedures one would
212 follow as a researcher that would result in compliance with MECIR. For example, RevMan does
213 not as an explicit step ask a research team to designate a librarian or information specialist as
214 part of an operational process that increases the effectiveness of search strategies for a review.

215 Also, while some aspects of reporting are automated by the simple provision in RevMan of a
216 structured template designed around PRISMA compliance, authors still manually enter
217 information based on their own separate documentation of their process, rather than the SR
218 report being directly generated from that data recorded in each operational step. Finally,
219 RevMan is optimised for one SR reporting task (completing a Cochrane review) rather than
220 designed to generate labelled data that can easily be repurposed for any SR reporting task.

221 Overall, we did not identify a tool that does all three tasks of interpreting a SR protocol into a
222 series of operational steps linked explicitly to SR conduct standards and reporting checklists,
223 collecting structured labelled data in completing those steps, and then automatically generating
224 draft documentation using that data.

225 *Potential strengths of our approach*

226 We believe our approach to a general-purpose SR protocol has three interrelated potential
227 advantages that can be further explored and developed. These are an emphasis on algorithmic
228 rather than heuristic approaches to conducting and reporting research, taking a view of conduct
229 standards and reporting checklists as being analogous to open-source software, and the
230 positioning of labelled data rather than a study manuscript as the primary output of the research
231 process. We discuss these briefly below.

232 *Algorithmic over heuristic approaches to conducting research*

233 Algorithms are a method for solving a problem in a finite number of steps via the application
234 of a set of formally-defined processes or rules. Heuristics are practical methods for problem-
235 solving that are derived from previous experiences with similar problems. Our opinion is that
236 systematic review is a design of study that tends to be conducted heuristically, but could be
237 made more accessible to researchers if formalised to be more algorithmic. Our general-purpose
238 protocol is an attempt to do this.

239 We note that our approach is algorithmic more in the sense of a detailed recipe in a cook-
240 book than in the more formal sense of being computable. A recipe formalises a sequence of
241 inputs (ingredients) and steps that need to be followed in order to generate an output (a
242 chocolate drip cake). The purpose of the recipe is to transfer expertise between cooks without
243 them having to physically meet, one to directly train another, or a cook having to intuit the recipe
244 from the ingredients and whatever cake-making experience they may have previously acquired.

245 Successfully following the recipe still requires experience and experimentation, but the purpose
246 of the recipe is to reduce that requirement: it means cooks don't have to remember or
247 internalise a full set of complex rules, making the possibility of successfully creating the final
248 dish more accessible.

249 Algorithmic protocols could similarly help with standard and checklist compliance. In codifying
250 a set of recommended practices and the recording of data outputs from following them,
251 compliance can become a byproduct of following the algorithm rather than something additional
252 that a researcher has to factor into the conduct and documentation of a study. This may help
253 address the problem of consistent under-reporting of key methodological information in SR
254 protocol registrations (Booth *et al.*, 2020) and, if extended beyond SR, also for primary studies
255 (Macleod *et al.*, 2021).

256 *Standards as open-source software*

257 Our approach makes it more transparent how the recommendations and requirements of one
258 or more conduct standards, or the requirements that are implicit in one or more reporting
259 checklists, have been interpreted into an operational procedure. Unlike static documents such
260 as the PRISMA checklist (Page *et al.*, 2021), we built our procedure in a platform that emulates
261 some aspects of software development. Protocols.io implements several GitHub-like
262 collaboration features (<https://github.com/>) that allow users of the general protocol to
263 independently build on and develop our prototype. These include allowing users to post
264 questions and comments on each step of the protocol (Figure 4), and to fork protocols for
265 independent development. Forking is particularly important for tracking versions of protocols.

266 Once an operational procedure has been written up and shared, it can be discussed, tested,
267 and finessed by those who are using it. Returning to our recipe analogy, cooks will modify
268 recipes for working in environments where an ingredient may need to be substituted for dietary
269 requirements, lack of availability, or for different tastes. Processes may be adapted for different
270 circumstances or levels of skill that may make some culinary techniques unrealistic to
271 implement. This is authoring, adapting, and versioning of the algorithm according to need.

272 Presenting the variations on a platform where relationships between versions are tracked
273 helps make adaptations discoverable and evaluable, and allows the evolution of processes to
274 be observed. It also implies an approach to standardisation that is more bottom-up and
275 responsive to community needs than the approaches traditionally recommended for developing

276 standards and checklists, such as the review-workshop-document process of Moher et al.
 277 (2014). We anticipate this resulting in clouds of related micro standards adapted around the
 278 specific needs of individual research communities. While this might sound chaotic to some,
 279 forking and versioning may allow adaptations of standards to be more transparent than the often
 280 unclear ways in which users currently interpret compliance with e.g. the PRISMA checklist.

281 **Figure 4:** An example of how a user can comment on a step of the protocol to suggest a feature or improvement. A
 282 user could also generate a fork of the protocol to add steps specific to their own requirements.

283 *Labelled data as primary, manuscripts as derivative*

284 Our approach positions labelled data as the primary output of the process of conducting a
 285 research activity, with documentation as a secondary output that is derived from labelled data.
 286 This reconfigures the conventional flow of data reuse in research, whereby data is generated, a
 287 document describing the acquisition and interpretation of data is published, and then
 288 researchers have to abstract from that document the data they need for reproducing or
 289 extending the original study.

290 When data, including data about methods, is labelled, compliance with a reporting checklist
 291 can become a matter of running code that generates a compliant manuscript, rather than
 292 retrospectively (and usually manually) cross-checking a document against a complex but routine
 293 set of reporting requirements. This kind of cross-checking is the sort of detailed but repetitive
 294 task that should be automated. Labelled data is also interoperable: code can be written to
 295 generate reports that are consistently compliant with one or more different reporting checklists.
 296 Availability of such code should reduce the requirement for an author of a SR protocol to be

297 experienced in any particular reporting format in order for them to produce a comprehensive,
 298 checklist-compliant report (illustrated in Figure 5).

299 **Figure 5:** Illustration of how the general-purpose protocol operationalises conduct standards into practical steps
 300 generating labelled data, which can be assembled into checklist-compliant protocol manuscripts. We believe this flow
 301 should be applicable to any study design, not just SR protocols.

302 **Current limitations and future development**

303 *Technical issues*

304 The proof-of-concept system described above is limited by a number of technical factors in
 305 our technology stack that need to be addressed via changes to the stack and/or development of
 306 the components within it.

307 Firstly is the difficulty in processing Microsoft Word documents in Python. Library support for
 308 templating, reading, and writing .docx files exists and is mature, but the feature set is limited.
 309 We found that existing libraries were not able to apply templates reliably, nor to inspect
 310 documents to separately extract text and tables in-order. This limited our templating features to
 311 basic inclusion of fields within running text, or concatenation of full documents (for example,

312 documents can only be concatenated by appending them to the end of a manuscript rather than
313 inserting them in the correct place; while they are in the correct order, the user needs to cut and
314 paste to the correct location). It also makes it easy to break our code, as it looks for text features
315 which if in a different place will not be found. Updating our protocol therefore has to be done
316 with care to preserve structure, which carries implicit rules and is therefore more likely to break.

317 Secondly, it is apparent that the format used by protocols.io to deliver data over their API is
318 primarily aimed at displaying such data via a web browser, that is, the content is difficult to
319 separate from its formatting. OSF records exhibit a similar issue: though every object within the
320 OSF system has a unique ID that makes referencing simple in principle, this ID is not exposed
321 to the end user except in certain circumstances, meaning it is difficult for users to link directly to
322 documents when completing a protocol run. This could be solved a number of ways, though
323 within our system we relied on unique filenames to identify entries.

324 Thirdly, data collection features in protocols.io are not yet well-developed. The platform has
325 been designed for recording bench protocols, with data collected mainly for the purpose of
326 process auditing and validation. We appropriated these data collection features for recording
327 data from completion of a step of the general purpose protocol, but with limited success. The
328 number of .docx documents that need to be uploaded to an OSF record is an example of a
329 workaround to address this issue. Allowing users to easily create richer documentation in-situ
330 would be preferable to creating and linking to a series of documents external to the general
331 protocol template.

332 Mitigating these limitations requires either significant software engineering effort using
333 current technology choices, or changing to a different technology stack. Regarding the latter, we
334 suggest changing the format used for templating to HTML, which has a much more mature
335 ecosystem of development tools, and later post-processing to convert to .docx formats if and
336 when required. Other languages and platforms (such as .net) may provide better support for
337 editing such formats.

338 *General development*

339 We only did enough development of our general-purpose protocol to prove the concept.
340 There could be additional operational steps to realise a more complete mapping of conduct and
341 reporting requirements, particularly for PROSPERO where administrative data is lacking from
342 our general protocol, and for item 16 of ROSES that asks for information about validation of

343 search strategy which we overlooked. Nor has our operationalisation been user-tested or
344 optimised. We also think that modularisation of our protocol would be helpful for improving the
345 efficiency of development and testing, and providing opportunities for finessing specific
346 components of the operationalised process independently on an as-needed basis, as per the
347 open software analogy discussed above. For example, we have previously created a protocol
348 for pilot-testing the screening process of a SR (Whaley, Garside and Eales, 2020), that could be
349 a module for step 21 of our general-purpose protocol.

350 While we have labelled data that allows computational assembly of protocol documentation,
351 our tooling does not yet extend to doing anything computational with the data that has been
352 labelled. Introducing and exploiting semantic authoring features for increased machine-
353 readability and more granular labelling that is integrated with ontologies would be beneficial for
354 a number of reasons (Whaley, Edwards, *et al.*, 2020), including interoperability of data between
355 systems and the validation of entered data.

356 We also note that conduct standards and reporting checklists are interventions that aim to
357 improve research quality via the dissemination of written instructions. We believe we have good
358 theoretical reasons for thinking our approach could be a more effective intervention than
359 conventional standards and checklists, but there is no empirical evidence that this is the case.
360 Therefore, there should be research into how effective our approach is, for whom it works best,
361 how much the granularity of operationalisation affects effectiveness, among other ideas. In
362 comparison to conventional approaches, our bottom-up approach to standardisation will have its
363 own challenges in relation to development, evaluation, and validation of the standards that are
364 produced, and the creation of suitable workflows for addressing them in what will be a nebulous
365 and distributed standards ecosystem.

366 Finally, even if the system is shown to be effective among users, there is no guarantee there
367 will be enough users of the system to make a difference to the general publishing standards
368 such systems seek to improve. We are encouraged by a recent pilot study that suggests
369 researchers may be open to increased formalisation of the reporting of study data (Wilkins *et al.*,
370 2022), and our approach is built on the assumption that automated research documentation will
371 incentivise use of operationalised protocols. However, we do not have a well-developed theory
372 based on empirical evidence as to what conditions need to be fulfilled in order for significant
373 uptake of a system such as we have prototyped. We subscribe to the view that infrastructure
374 should be viewed broadly as an installed base of both technology and social arrangements,

375 including group membership and conventions of practice (Edwards *et al.*, 2009), and that
 376 successfully securing uptake of systems analogous to ours will require both to be addressed.

377 Conclusion

378 We have presented a general purpose SR protocol that is intended to serve as a proof-of-
 379 concept for improving compliance with SR conduct standards and reporting checklists,
 380 principally by reducing the experience requirement for successfully using such standards and
 381 checklists in a research process. We articulated some of the potential advantages of our
 382 approach, including viewing the problem of compliance as benefiting from an algorithm-like
 383 solution, treating the development of research standards and checklists as being analogous to
 384 open-source software development, and the positioning of labelled data as the primary output of
 385 research from which a manuscript is a derivative product. We acknowledge a range of issues
 386 with our existing technology stack, and outline a plan for further development that includes
 387 technical development and the generation of empirical evidence for the effectiveness of our
 388 proposed approach.

389 Supporting Information (Data, Code, and Research Materials)

Item	Link
Document templates for complex protocol data that cannot be directly entered into the general-purpose protocol	https://osf.io/h7w68/
List of labels for the protocol data	https://osf.io/vw4e3
Labelled template for generating automated protocol documentation	https://osf.io/nckwu
Draft protocol from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/zr78y
JSON database from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/63tmz
PDF of data entered into Protocols.io on test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/t3z98
Full set of documents created for test run and uploaded to OSF as per general-purpose protocol instructions (test run #7)	https://osf.io/m35px/
Code for JSON conversion from Protocols.io protocol run and document generation	https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD

390

391 **Metadata**

392 **Funding**

393 Lancaster University Impact Acceleration Award: “TARPD Prototype Tool for Automated
394 Research Project Documentation”

395 **Preregistration**

396 This study was not preregistered.

397 **Declaration of Interests**

398 PW declares the following financial interests: consultancy services for the Evidence-Based
399 Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public
400 Health; Lancaster University, mainly around securing impact of his PhD research (completed
401 2020); the University of Central Lancashire (UCLAN), which has involved developing furniture
402 fire safety models relevant to reducing the impact of the use of chemical flame retardants in
403 ensuring fire safety for the UK Government Agency OPSS; and for Yordas Group, to deliver
404 training in SR methods for EU JRC. PW also receives an Honorarium as Systematic Reviews
405 Editor for the journal Environment International. In general, PW’s consultancy work is around
406 development and promotion of systematic review methods in environmental health research,
407 delivering training around these methods, and providing editorial services. He is applying for
408 funding to develop evidence surveillance and automated SR documentation methods through
409 Lancaster University, which if successful will arrive within the next two years.

410 PW also declares the following non-financial interests: a historical, public commitment to high
411 quality systematic review methods in support of environmental health policy and decision-
412 making; active involvement in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in
413 evidence synthesis. These include development of SR conduct standards (e.g. COSTER),
414 reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage, IV-CAT) to
415 support the production of high quality systematic reviews, evidence maps, and other study
416 designs. PW is an active member of the GRADE Working Group, has a senior role at EBTC that
417 involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental
418 health, and is a member of an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy
419 in the UK, and several Brussels-based environmental policy advocacy groups including HEAL

420 and EEB. In general, PW has a strong interest in supporting precautionary, evidence-based
421 approaches to environmental health policy.

422 SW declares providing scientific & technical consultancy services as a subcontractor to PW
423 on a UK OPSS-funded study into the use of chemical fire retardants in furniture. SW has also
424 provided scientific consultancy services in unrelated fields, and states that publication of work in
425 any area impacts chances of future employment.

426 AMS declares that, as part of her role at Bond University, she provides training in: evidence-
427 based medicine and systematic review methodology (including automation tools), to Australia-
428 based academics, clinicians and students. Those workshops charge a registration fee. AMS is
429 part of the Systematic Review Accelerator team at Bond University, which develops and makes
430 publicly available automation tools to accelerate completion of systematic reviews, as well as
431 conducting research in this area (all tools are available free of charge). From October 2022,
432 AMS will be an Associate Editor for Systematic Reviews, a BMC / Springer Nature journal (non-
433 remunerated).

434 JV is a Senior Research Associate at Lancaster University and declares having no interests
435 that may compromise the integrity of the research described in this manuscript.

436 **Ethics Declarations**

437 Ethical approval and informed consent were not required for this research, as it involved neither
438 human nor animal participants.

439 **Data availability**

440 All data is available from the accompanying OSF project record at
441 <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZJEVP> and GitHub repository at
442 <https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD>

443 **Authors' Contributions**

444 *Created using Tenzing app (Holcombe et al., 2020).*

445 Conceptualization: Paul Whaley. Data curation: Stephen Wattam. Funding acquisition: Paul
446 Whaley and John Vidler. Investigation: Paul Whaley and Stephen Wattam. Methodology: Paul
447 Whaley and Stephen Wattam. Project administration: John Vidler. Software: Stephen Wattam.
448 Supervision: John Vidler. Validation: Stephen Wattam. Visualisation: Paul Whaley and Stephen

449 Wattam. Writing - original draft: Paul Whaley. Writing - review & editing: Paul Whaley, Stephen
450 Wattam, Anna Mae Scott and John Vidler.

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